

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Metal-free Hydrogen Generation from Seawater and Silicon Waste: A Circular Approach

 Mustapha Hamdaoui | Anja Steinmaurer | Philipp Jernej | Daniel Legenstein | Peter Hartmann |
 Adrian Daniel Boese

Institute of Chemistry, University of Graz, Graz, Austria

Correspondence: Mustapha Hamdaoui (mustapha.hamdaoui@uni-graz.at) | Katalin Barta (katalin.barta@uni-graz.at)

Received: 16 February 2026 | **Revised:** 28 April 2026 | **Accepted:** 18 May 2026

Keywords: hydrogen | metal-free catalysis | polymer recycling | seawater | waste silicon

ABSTRACT

Hydrogen is a primordial energy carrier and industrial raw material that will play a crucial role in future energy transition and decarbonization ambitions. Silane hydrolysis represents an under-explored approach to hydrogen generation, yet most known systems have thus far focused on noble-metal catalysis. Herein we report a highly active transition metal-free method for the production of hydrogen from (sea)water and hydrosilanes, relying on the unique combination of simple bases as catalyst, and dimethyl sulfoxide as promoting solvent, assisted by mechanistic and computational studies. Remarkably, the hydrolysis of phenylsilane achieved a turnover frequency (TOF) of $202 \pm 5 \text{ min}^{-1}$, far superior to existing metal-free systems ($\text{TOF} \leq 8 \text{ min}^{-1}$), and even surpassing noble-metal catalysts ($\text{TOF} \leq 170 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The developed method rapidly generates hydrogen directly from seawater, applying polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS), a silicon industry waste, with rates up to $70.2 \text{ mol}_{\text{H}_2}/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}/\text{h}$. Notably, we have demonstrated the recyclability of the solvent, and re-use of the by-products formed during PMHS hydrolysis. Thus, the polysiloxane by-products were efficiently depolymerized into functional chlorosilane monomers, which are suitable for the design of new high-value silicon polymers. These findings highlight the broader applicability and circularity of our integrated approach.

1 | Introduction

Hydrogen (H_2) is a centrally important chemical energy carrier and industrial raw material [1, 2]. While the promise of green H_2 struggles in realizing its foreseen global implementation [1], even the most pessimistic scenarios anticipate that H_2 will still play a growing role in future high-value industrial processes [1]. In the net-zero scenario, the global demand of H_2 is estimated to be nearly 400 Mt by 2050 (Figure S1) [3]. Currently, the vast majority of H_2 originates from fossil resources through coal gasification (22%), natural gas reforming (60%) and industry by-product (e.g., refineries; >15%), overall resulting in about 920 Mt/annum CO_2 emissions [4]. Thus, it is critically important to develop an array of novel methods for clean hydrogen production (Figure S2) [5]. Beside the most mature technology, namely water electrolysis, it

is also interesting to consider catalytic methods for sustainable hydrogen generation [6–8].

A robust method for H_2 generation from water, which is not electricity-driven, is through hydrolysis of hydrosilanes. Previously, silane hydrolysis was predominantly achieved using (noble) transition metal catalysts [9–22]. The industrial scalability of siloxane-based liquid hydrogen carriers is currently being pioneered by HSL Technologies (formerly HySiLabs) [23]. This reaction could be rendered much more sustainable and cost-effective by switching to metal-free systems. Indeed, the activation of the Si–H bond in the absence of a transition metal was achieved by Grubbs, Stoltz, Zare and coworkers, showing that simple bases could be utilized as catalysts in the silylation of C–H [24–26] and O–H [27] bonds. Albeit seldom studied,

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* published by Wiley-VCH GmbH

pioneering reports showed feasibility of silane hydrolysis under metal-free conditions, but the performance remained still far inferior to the transition metal systems [28–32]. Moreover, the use of potentially hazardous organic solvents and/or additives [33] [e.g., *N,N'*-dimethylpropylene urea (DMPU) [28], hexamethylphosphoramide (HMPA) [30], tetrahydrofuran (THF) [31]; Table S1], the predominant reliance on non-waste hydrosilanes [34], and the lack of information about key catalytic intermediates as well as experimental demonstration of the recyclability of the studied systems are major weaknesses of previous systems.

More specifically, in their elegant study, Yang and coworkers [28] have found an accelerating effect of DMPU, a reprototoxic chemical, on the hydrolysis of hydrosilanes without the need for additional base. Other similar aprotic dipolar solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylformamide (DMF) did not show the same accelerating effect under these conditions (Table S1). The Fan group [31] reported the hydrolysis of various hydrosilanes in the presence of KOH in deionized (DI) water, in THF as co-solvent, at room temperature (RT), albeit with moderate efficiency. Brunel has demonstrated that 85% yield H₂ could be generated from DI-H₂O and hydrosilanes using a combination of 30% NaOH and 1.5 mol% HMPA [30]. Similarly to DMPU, HMPA is also known for its high toxicity, and it would be necessary to find suitable alternatives [35–37]

Here we describe the surprising accelerating effect of DMSO, an innocuous and biodegradable solvent [33],[35], in combination with simple bases as catalysts, on silane hydrolysis (Figure 1B). Remarkably, the here-developed method led to unprecedented hydrolysis rates applicable to a range of hydrosilanes. For instance, the hydrolysis of phenylsilane achieved a turnover frequency (TOF) of $202 \pm 5 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Table S2), far superior to existing metal-free systems ($\text{TOF} \leq 8 \text{ min}^{-1}$) and even outperformed the best transition metal-based catalysts ($\text{TOF} \leq 170 \text{ min}^{-1}$). Mechanistic details were scrutinized through a combined synthetic, spectroscopic and computational approach, and an ionic mechanism [25] was proposed based on the isolation and spectroscopic characterization of a key pentavalent ionic silane intermediate $\text{K}[\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OtBu})]$.

Having a powerful method for H₂ generation in hand, we next addressed broader sustainability and circularity challenges related to feedstock availability, and recycling / re-use of solvents and byproducts. Conceptually, a highly attractive approach would be to integrate hydrogen generation with silicon-waste valorization using affordable feedstocks: seawater and readily available industrial polymeric waste. Of particular interest is polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS), which contains many reactive hydride units (ca. 25–35 [38] per polymer unit). Thus, we envisioned an integrated approach where the waste hydrosilane PMHS is valorized into H₂ using seawater while the silicone resin co-generated in the process is repurposed or recycled (Figure 1B).

In this context, we have shown that, using non-treated seawater and PMHS, an impressive 1600 mL of H₂ can be produced in under one minute using only 6.5 g of PMHS waste and 1 mL of untreated seawater ($\text{TOF} = 43.8 \text{ min}^{-1}$). Subsequently, the solvent was recycled and reused in catalysis while the generated, water insoluble polysiloxane (abbreviated as Si resin) was removed by simple filtration and efficiently depolymerized under mild con-

ditions. The here-developed powerful depolymerization method yields MeSiCl₃ and MeSiCl₂OH, valuable building blocks for the synthesis of various silicone materials [39] (Figure 1A).

2 | Results and Discussion

As earlier stated, our ultimate goal was to identify a novel metal-free catalytic method for the rapid generation of H₂ from seawater and waste PMHS as abundantly available and benign feedstock, and devise a viable strategy for the recycling and/or repurposing of the silicone resin co-generated in the process. First, we describe the set of experiments aimed at identifying a highly active metal-free catalytic system for hydrogen generation from water and a series of hydrosilanes bearing alkyl or phenyl substituents. Next, we evaluated the mechanistic aspects of the catalytic system by a combined experimental, spectroscopic and computational approach.

In the last section, we discuss the results and implications of metal-free hydrogen generation from seawater integrated with Si waste recycling.

2.1 | The Development of a Novel Method for Hydrogen Generation From Silanes

2.1.1 | Impact of DMSO on the Hydrogen Generation Rate

Based on prior work, we first studied the impact of several solvent systems on the H₂ generation from water and hydrosilanes, using catalytic amounts of inexpensive, innocuous bases. HSiEt₃ was chosen as it reacts sluggishly with water under basic conditions, thus allowing for more accurate and reliable comparison between the different measurements. The reaction efficiency was evaluated by directly measuring the released H₂ volume $V_{(\text{H}_2)}$ as function of time and comparing the initial reaction rates derived from the time-dependent $V_{(\text{H}_2)}$ data (Figure S3).

The results of hydrogen generation in different solvent systems, using triethylsilane (HSiEt₃) and DI-water as well as 5 mol% of KOtBu are displayed in Figure 2. Interestingly, the silane hydrolysis rate was found dominant in DMSO, compared to all other solvents tested. Specifically, in the presence of DMSO, 98% yield of H₂ ($V_{(\text{H}_2)} \approx 24 \text{ mL}$; max. theoretical $V_{(\text{H}_2)} \approx 24.5 \text{ mL}$) was released in >15 min corresponding to an initial reaction rate of $1.02 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mM/min}$ (Table S3). While in all other solvents tested, only $\leq 10\%$ H₂ was released in 30 min, corresponding to initial reaction rates ranging 1.18×10^{-2} – $4.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mM/min}$, which are 10–100 times lower than that obtained using DMSO.

2.1.2 | Impact of the Base Catalyst

Next, a series of organic and inorganic base catalysts of varying pK_b (Table S4) [40, 41] were evaluated using HSiEt₃ and DI-water, using 5 mol% base. The results are shown in Figure 3. Control experiments conducted without base or without HSiEt₃ showed no hydrogen generation. A general trend was observed, where relatively weak bases (NaOAc, NaOPiv and K₂CO₃) showed almost

FIGURE 1 | The integrated approach developed in this paper for the metal-free hydrogen generation from water and waste silicon.

no catalytic activity, while stronger bases (NaOH, KOH, KOMe and KOtBu) afforded much improved hydrogen generation rates. The catalytic activity increased in the order: NaOH < KOMe < KOH ≤ KOtBu. However, although very similar initial reaction rates were observed for both KOH (1.01 × 10⁻¹ mM/min) and KOtBu (1.04 × 10⁻¹ mM/min), a somewhat higher H₂ yield was obtained for KOtBu (V_(H₂) ≈ 24.1 mL; 98% yield) versus KOH (V_(H₂) ≈ 22.4 mL; 91% yield). For this reason, KOtBu was used for all further studies.

The better performance of KOtBu and KOH in catalyzing the hydrogen generation from water and HSiEt₃ may be explained by their higher basicity, when compared to the other bases tested (Table S4). Further screening of the base loading showed that 5

mol% KOtBu gave optimal conversion and reaction rate (Figures S4-5; Table S5).

2.1.3 | Impact of the Hydrosilane

In order to probe the effect of varying the substituent at silicon in the hydrosilane, HSiEt₃ was compared with diethylsilane (Et₂SiH₂), phenylsilane (PhSiH₃) and polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS). PMHS is particularly interesting because it is an abundant and cheap waste derived from the silicon industry [42], besides being bench stable and non-toxic liquid with a relatively low boiling point (142°C) [38]. While the PMHS utilized in our standardized laboratory studies was obtained from commercial

FIGURE 2 | The effect of different solvents + control experiment without any added solvent on the volume of hydrogen generated from the reaction of H_2O and HSiEt_3 . Conditions: HSiEt_3 (129 mg, 1.11 mmol), H_2O (0.02 mL, 1.11 mmol), KOtBu (6.23 mg, 0.055 mmol), DMSO (0.5 mL). The maximum theoretical V_{H_2} that can be released from 1.11 mmol H_2O is ≈ 24.5 mL.

FIGURE 3 | The effect of different catalysts + control experiment without any added base on the volume of hydrogen generated from the reaction of H_2O and HSiEt_3 . Conditions: HSiEt_3 (129 mg, 1.11 mmol), H_2O (0.02 mL, 1.11 mmol), KOtBu (6.23 mg, 0.055 mmol), DMSO (0.5 mL). The maximum theoretical V_{H_2} that can be released from 1.11 mmol H_2O is ≈ 24.5 mL.

sources to ensure kinetic reproducibility, PMHS on an industrial scale represents a massive, underutilized waste by-product of the Müller-Rochow process. Figure 4 provides a comparison of the hydrogen generation kinetics for all the selected hydrosilanes. PhSiH_3 , Et_2SiH_2 and PMHS show outstanding kinetics with respect to hydrogen generation. In the case of PhSiH_3 89% H_2 is generated in <25 s, corresponding to an initial reaction rate of 9.06×10^{-1} mM/min and an impressive TOF of 202 ± 5 min^{-1} (calculated for the first H_2 equivalent; see Figure S6 and Movie

FIGURE 4 | The effect of different hydrosilanes on the volume of hydrogen generated from the reaction of H_2O and HSiEt_3 , Et_2SiH_2 , PhSiH_3 and PMHS. Conditions: hydrosilane (1.11 mmol), H_2O (0.02 mL, 1.11 mmol), KOtBu (6.23 mg, 0.055 mmol), DMSO (0.5 mL). The maximum theoretical $V_{(\text{H}_2)\text{theo.}}$ that can be released from reaction of 1.11 mmol H_2O with HSiEt_3 is ≈ 24.5 mL. For other cases, due to the availability of at least of two hydrides that can react with the two protons of H_2O , the expected maximum is $V_{(\text{H}_2)\text{theo.}} \approx 49$ mL.

S1), which is much higher compared to metal-free or transition metal-based systems (Table S2).

In the case of PMHS, 65% H_2 yield was achieved in <60 s corresponding to an initial reaction rate of $7, 25 \times 10^{-1}$ mM/min and an excellent TOF of 43.8 min^{-1} . This reaction continued to evolve hydrogen for 5 min yielding a total of 76% H_2 yield. Et_2SiH_2 was also found to be a very potent hydride source for this reaction since 61% H_2 yield is generated in <60 s corresponding to an initial reaction rate of $7, 02 \times 10^{-1}$ mM/min and a TOF ≈ 40 min^{-1} . Compared to other silanes, HSiEt_3 performed the worst with an initial reaction rate of 1.02×10^{-1} mM/min.

2.2 | Mechanistic Considerations

2.2.1 | Analysis of the Silicon Byproducts

The reaction between HSiEt_3 and DI H_2O (1:1 ratio) in the presence of 5 mol% KOtBu was monitored by in situ NMR analysis in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ (Figure S7). The resulting ^1H spectrum showed a resonance peak at 4.56 ppm identified as H_2 alongside those attributed to the Si by-products ($\text{Et}_3\text{SiOSiEt}_3$ and HOSiEt_3). This NMR assignment was confirmed by comparison with NMR spectra of the isolated two fractions following a bulb-to-bulb vacuum distillation (Figures S7/S10). ^{29}Si NMR spectra showed that the resonance peak of HSiEt_3 at 7 ppm disappeared and a new signal of the disiloxane product $\text{Et}_3\text{SiOSiEt}_3$ was observed at ca. 9 ppm; the ^{29}Si resonance for HOSiEt_3 expected at ca. 18 ppm [43] could not be detected most likely because of its low concentration. Further analysis of the reaction mixture via gas chromatography (GC-MS) confirmed the formation of both Si by-products HOSiEt_3 and $\text{Et}_3\text{SiOSiEt}_3$ (Figures S9/S11).

2.2.2 | Analysis of the Evolved Gas

To further confirm that H₂ was indeed generated, the gas evolved from the reaction mixture was bubbled into a solution of toluene-*d*₈. Direct ¹H NMR analysis of the latter solution revealed only one resonance singlet peak at 4.50 ppm that is unambiguously assigned to H₂ (Figure S12). GC analysis using a thermal-coupled detector (TCD) also confirmed that H₂ was indeed the only gas generated (Figure S13). Indirect detection of H₂ was also employed, using cyclohexene as the substrate of hydrogenation (Figure S14). This reaction was chosen because it was reported to be readily catalyzed using Pd/C at RT and 1 atmosphere of H₂ [44]. The complete hydrogenation of cyclohexene was observed (99% GC yield), further confirming the generation of H₂ (Figure S15).

While other gases (e.g., methane, ethane) could potentially evolve from the decomposition of DMSO or HSiEt₃, none could be detected. Control experiments showed that negligible traces of water were present in either DMSO and HSiEt₃ (Figure S16, Table S6). In addition, several controls ruled out the potential formation of SiMe₂ from the deoxygenation of DMSO in the presence of HSiEt₃ (Figures S17–19) [45]. For instance, catalysis experiments using isotopically labelled H₂¹⁸O demonstrated that the oxygen incorporated in the Si byproducts originated from water and not from DMSO (Figures S20,21).

2.2.3 | On the Potential Contribution from Transition-metal, Radical or Light Mediated Catalysis

In order to rule out noble metal contamination [46, 47] analysis by ICP-MS (inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry) of the DMSO and KO*t*Bu samples used throughout this study revealed a negligible metal content (e.g., Ag, Pt, Pd, Rh, Ir ≤ 50 ppb; more data in Table S7). Next, we probed the change of kinetics of H₂ generation induced by the addition of 10 ppm of different metal precursors to the standard metal-free catalysis mixture (Figure S22) with no deviations found. Further orthogonal poisoning experiments using strong aprotic metal chelators (10 mol% 2,2'-bipyridine or triphenylphosphine) showed no deviation in the hydrogen evolution kinetics (Figure S24), further confirming that the rapid catalysis is most likely a metal-free process independent of trace transition metal impurities.

No abnormal deviation in catalysis rates were determined in controls verifying the possible involvement of trace metals or other impurities that might originate either from different chemical suppliers or material (e.g., stir bar, borosilicate glass) used for the reaction (Figures S23 & 25–27). Further controls of the H₂O/Et₃SiH/KO*t*Bu/DMSO system indicated no contribution from radical- [48] or photo-initiation [49, 50] to the reaction mechanism (Figure S28).

2.2.4 | Isolation of a Catalytic Intermediate and Its Reactivity

Next, we aimed at delineating the roles of KO*t*Bu and DMSO in our catalysis system. Previous work [51] has shown that reactions

FIGURE 5 | (A) Reported work on the generation of the anionic pentacoordinate Si intermediate from tetravalent silanes and nucleophilic catalyst, and its subsequent reactivity with stoichiometric nucleophiles [51, 52]. (B) Isolation of the new anionic pentacoordinate Si intermediate K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] and its reactivity towards H₂O, MeOH and DMSO (*this work*).

of tetravalent silanes with nucleophilic catalysts (e.g., F⁻, RO⁻, HMPA) give an anionic pentacoordinate Si intermediate which subsequently reacts with nucleophiles at the silicon atom to give new silicon products, releasing leaving group X⁻ (Figure 5A). For instance, Corriu and coworkers [52] have observed instantaneous hydrogen evolution when the pentacoordinate species K[HSi(O-*i*Pr)₄] was mixed with H₂O. No reaction occurred between HSi(O-*i*Pr)₃ and H₂O alone after 5 days.

Using the synthetic procedure developed by Corriu [52], we have isolated a novel anionic pentacoordinate Si intermediate K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] in 17% yield by reaction of HSi(OEt)₃ with 1 equiv. of KO*t*Bu in THF (RT, 4 h) (Figures 5B; SI, section 9a). Such a hydrosilicate ion bearing a *tert*-butoxy moiety is the subject of a growing debate in the literature, especially from the perspective of mechanistic investigation of the Stoltz–Grubbs KO*t*Bu–Et₃SiH system [24, 25, 48, 53]. Many organosilicates were previously characterized by NMR spectroscopy and/or X-ray diffraction [54, 55] To our best knowledge, the new silicate adduct K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] represents the first *tert*-butoxy-based silicate species from alkoxide/hydrosilane systems to be isolated and analytically characterized. The similar species Na[H₂Si(Ph)₂(O*t*Bu)] was observed by in situ NMR studies only and could not be isolated due to its high fluxional behavior and reactivity [53].

Next, the potential role of K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] during catalysis was investigated by conducting a series of stoichiometric reactions with DI-H₂O, MeOH and DMSO (NMR in toluene-*d*₈) (SI, section 9b). First, reaction of K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] with MeOH revealed the formation of the expected products MeOSiEt₃, KO*t*Bu and H₂, whereas the same reaction with H₂O led to the exhaustive hydrolysis of K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] into mainly Si(OH)₄ and EtOH, accompanied by H₂ and KO*t*Bu. However, when K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] was mixed with DMSO (53 equiv.), ca. 50% of K[HSi(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] was converted to the presumed adduct K[HSi(DMSO)(OEt)₃(O*t*Bu)] whereby DMSO coordinates to Si. The latter observation could explain in part the specific

FIGURE 6 | (A) Previous mechanistic studies by Shubina et al. [59]. (B) Our proposed mechanism for the silane hydrolysis developed in this study. (C) DFT calculations of the energy diagram of the proposed mechanism of the reaction of Me_3SiH with H_2O , assuming OH^- and OtBu^- to be the catalyst (abbreviated OY^-), respectively and employing the COSMO implicit solvation model. An extended version that also accounts for possible subsequent reaction steps can be found in the SI. To be able to compare both OH^- and OtBu^- on the same energetic scale, OH^- was chosen as the energetic reference and the reaction energy of HotBu with OH^- was used to determine the energy of the free educts in the OtBu^- case.

accelerating effect induced by DMSO during catalysis, due to its role in stabilizing anionic intermediates such as $\text{K}[\text{HSiR}_3(\text{OtBu})]$ [56–58]

Finally, when $\text{K}[\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OtBu})]$ was used as catalyst (5 mol%) in the reaction of $\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3$ with $\text{DI-H}_2\text{O}$ in the presence of DMSO, the hydrogen evolution kinetics were very similar to those observed for the reaction involving KOtBu as catalyst (Figure S44; SI, section 9c). Thus, along with the above observations, this experiment strongly suggests the involvement of the adduct of general formula $\text{K}[\text{HSiR}_3(\text{OY})]$ ($\text{OY} = \text{OtBu}, \text{OH}$; **int-A** in Figure 6) as a plausible catalytic intermediate in the silane hydrolysis reaction, which is also supported by our computations (see below).

2.2.5 | An Ionic Reaction Mechanism Is Proposed

Based on our experimental observations and the prior work of Voronova et al. [59], who studied the *stoichiometric* methanolysis of diphenylsilane (Ph_2SiH_2), we propose a mechanism for our metal-free catalyzed silane hydrolysis (Figure 6B) and set out on a preliminary computational study to further validate its plausibility. To account for the formation of the disiloxane $\text{Et}_3\text{SiOEt}_3$ as the major Si byproduct, a mechanism is proposed in Figure S45.

DFT calculations of the energy profile were conducted using the simplified silane model HSiMe_3 to eliminate any potential influence of the conformational space (the results were subse-

quently verified with calculations on the HSiEt_3 system revealing that the qualitative picture is retained; see SI). While the OtBu -bound intermediate provides a structurally isolated baseline, the rapid equilibrium with water suggests that hydroxide (OH^-) is also a highly likely active catalytic species under standard reaction conditions. Thus, due to the complex nature of the water-DMSO system and largely comparable results between KOH and KOtBu , we opted to carry out our computational investigations with both OH^- and OtBu^- as potential catalysts (denoted collectively OY^-). At this stage of the study, we speculate that the prompting effect of DMSO is due to the great solvation of K^+ , yielding the highly reactive ‘naked’ pentavalent silicate nucleophiles.

In the first step of the mechanism, the base anion OY^- adds to the electrophilic silicon atom of HSiR_3 to yield the pentavalent intermediate $[\text{HSiR}_3(\text{OY})]^-$ (**int-A**). Whereas this addition could, *a priori*, lead to either an axial or equatorial arrangement of the OY moiety in **int-A**, our calculations indicate the axial species to lead to the overall lower energy pathway, which is in accordance with the work of Voronova and coworkers [59] (a detailed comparison of the axial and equatorial reaction pathways is given in the SI, section 9e). Formation of **int-A** is highly endergonic for both investigated catalysts ($\Delta G_{\text{OH}^-} = 47.7$ kJ/mol and $\Delta G_{\text{OtBu}^-} = 63.8$ kJ/mol). Next, adduct complex **int-B** is generated by H_2O forming a dihydride $\text{H}^{\delta-} \cdots \text{H}^{\delta+}$ interaction [60] with the silicon-bound hydrogen, which is conceptually analogous to ammonia borane systems [61]. Additionally, we propose that the coordination of the base catalyst to the silane leads to an increased hydride character in the involved hypervalent pentacoordinate

species. Indeed, NMR data showed a shielded ^1H resonance for the hydride in isolated $\text{K}[\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OtBu})]$ compared to free $\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3$ (SI, section 9a). Together, these factors manifest in a very low additional activation energy for the subsequent **TS1**, where the H-Si bond breaks to form a hydride (**int-C**). Nevertheless, **TS1** constitutes the overall highest energy barrier in the reaction mechanism and is, hence, rate determining. Overall, the OH^- pathway is energetically favored ($\Delta\Delta G = 24.1$ kJ/mol). Subsequently, one hydrogen atom from water binds with the hydride from HSiR_3 (**TS2**), thereby generating an agglomerate of the reaction products Me_3SiOY , H_2 and OH^- (**prod**). Subsequent escape of H_2 and dissolution of the agglomerate reveals the overall reaction to be highly exergonic irrespective of the investigated catalyst. In sum, the reaction of **int-A** with H_2O generates one equivalent of H_2 alongside one equivalent of HOSiR_3 , thereby regenerating the base catalyst.

Overall, the computational data predict OH^- to be a much more effective catalyst than OtBu^- . Judging from the $\text{p}K_{\text{A}}$ values of HOtBu and H_2O in DMSO, which are 32.2 and 31.4, respectively, the equilibrium can also be slightly expected to favor OH^- . Together with the similarity of the respective V_{H_2} vs time curves in Figure 2, and the generation of hydroxide during the reaction, this suggest the main catalytically active species to be OH^- for both KOtBu and KOH catalytic systems. The postulated mechanism is also in line with the experimental isolation and catalytic activity of $\text{K}[\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OtBu})]$. Contrary to its congeners $\text{HSiMe}_3(\text{OY})$ and $\text{HSiEt}_3(\text{OY})$ (see Figure 6C and the SI/section 9e, respectively), which display very high Gibbs free energies, the formation of $\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OY})$ is computationally predicted to be energetically stable enough to be isolable [$\Delta G(\text{OtBu}) = +9.3$ kJ/mol; see the SI for details]. When subjected to water, $\text{HSi}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{OtBu})$ can be expected to readily undergo reaction, releasing OH^- and H_2 in the process, with the former potentially playing an active role throughout the subsequent reaction cycles.

2.3 | Towards an integrated and circular strategy to derive hydrogen from silicon waste and seawater

2.3.1 | Hydrogen Generation From Seawater and Waste PMHS

Planet Earth is 97% covered with seawater, yet conversion of this abundant natural source into H_2 is still at its infancy. Electrolysis of seawater to H_2 is the most promising approach [62–65]. Much research is currently directed to increasing the performance of electrolyzers against the deleterious effect of chloride and other anions originating from the various salts present in seawater. Additional concerns include elimination of environmental hazards and reducing contributions to climate change from the release of chlorine and other gases [62]. The approach presented in this paper represents a possible alternative for H_2 generation, by directly using non-treated seawater through silane hydrolysis. Thus, gratifyingly we observed that H_2 can indeed be readily produced from Mediterranean seawater instead of DI water, without any significant changes to the hydrogen evolution kinetics. As a proof-of-concept, 1600 mL H_2 could be generated in less one minute using 1 mL of seawater and 6.5 g of PMHS [38] (Figure 7). While controlled-addition experiments (15°C) successfully suppressed initial H_2 bursts, late-

stage acceleration due to resin viscosity indicates that achieving steady-state flow requires dedicated reactor engineering (Figure S65). Likewise, high efficiencies were observed when using other seawater sources (Figure S66). These results showcase promise for future medium to large scale applications where on-site and on-demand hydrogen is rapidly needed using non-treated seawater, while alleviating some of the drawbacks associated with the electrolysis method (e.g., chlorine release). As detailed in the Supporting Information (SI-section 3), calculations based on global silicone production metrics demonstrate that valorizing the unavoidable PMHS waste stream could sustainably generate kiloton-scale volumes (e.g., >1,600 metric tons [66] of high-purity hydrogen annually from a single, underutilized source. Control experiments confirmed that seawater ions neither inhibit the catalytic kinetics (Figure S67) nor contaminate the final product, as residual salts are readily removed via a simple water/methanol wash prior to resin recycling (see SI section 12).

2.3.2 | Recovery, Reuse and Recyclability

The reaction of PMHS with water, under specific catalytic conditions, yields a cross-linked silicone resin structurally assignable to a polysilsesquioxane of T-type bonding motif (formally as ' RSiO_3 ' monomeric formula) [67]. This T-type structure results from the condensation of the in situ generated silanol units $\text{Me}_n\text{Si}(\text{OH})_m\text{O}_y$. Because of its low miscibility in aqueous or organic media, the silicone resin precipitates from the reaction medium as a white solid, allowing for recovery and repurposing into either new silicone materials [68], silicone adhesives (e.g., in skin adhesion [69]) or as siloxane-based water repellents for the building industry [70] (e.g., Wacker Chemie AG is actively developing sustainable silicone materials for the cement durability).

Thus, in the reactions involving PMHS-based H_2 generation, we have observed the formation of a white silicone resin (Si Resin; Figure 7), and envisioned a recycling strategy where DMSO could be recovered and reused, while the Si resin could be selectively degraded into usable Si monomers (Figure 7).

For the recovery of the solvent, the resin contaminated with both DMSO and KOtBu was subjected to vacuum distillation, with 96% DMSO recovery in high purity (Figure S68), while recovery of KOtBu was not attempted due to its catalytic use. To confirm reusability in practical applications, the recovered DMSO was utilized across three consecutive hydrogen generation cycles; remarkably, no significant change in catalytic activity or kinetic performance was observed (see SI, Figure S69 for full kinetic profiles).

While very challenging to achieve, selective chemical recycling of this silicone resin into high-value Si monomeric building blocks is vital for a circular strategy herein, and would be highly promising for the silicone industry overall [39]. Thus, we next dealt with repurposing the dried resin. Its molecular structure was determined by solution ^1H NMR (Figure S70), solid state ^{29}Si NMR (Figure S71) as well as infrared spectroscopy (Figure S78). As expected, all analyses showed that the resin is a result of the oxidation of the Si-H moieties of PMHS into silanols,

FIGURE 7 | Demonstration of the integrated approach described in this study: Hydrogen generated from the reaction of sea H_2O and PMHS in combination with the proposed recycling strategy. Conditions: PMHS (6.5 g, 111 mmol), H_2O (1 mL, 55.5 mmol), KOtBu (62 mg, 27.5 mmol), DMSO (2 mL). The maximum theoretical $V_{(\text{H}_2)\text{theo}}$ that can be released from the reaction of 55.5 mmol sea H_2O with 111 mmol PMHS is ≈ 2486 mL (if the two H atoms of H_2O are consumed).

which then self-condense into siloxane bridges (Figure 7). These monomeric units can be compared to T-resin monomers. The presence of such monomers would suggest the formation of polysilsesquioxanes, which was confirmed by comparison to independently synthesized Si resins with established structures (Figures S72–77) [71].

Döhlert and Enthaler presented the degradation of silicon byproducts, into the volatile monomers MeSiHF_2 and MeSiF_3 using $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{OEt}_2$ [72]. The main drawbacks of this approach are the use of excess $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{OEt}_2$, the elevated temperature and the regeneration of gaseous monomers. Another promising method leverages the catalytic activity of tetrabutylammonium fluoride in THF to depolymerize various silicone polysiloxane materials at room temperature [73, 74]. Unfortunately, while we observed extensive degradation of our Si-resin using this approach, the resulting Si monomers could not be adequately identified.

Hence, we applied the two alternative methods A and B (Figure 7) [39]. In method A, pioneered by Montail, Raynaud and coworkers, BCl_3 was combined with catalytic FeCl_3 in dichloromethane (DCM) at 45°C for the depolymerization of our Si resin, yet the process was incomplete (SI, section 12). Therefore, we have developed a dual catalytic approach, by applying both AlCl_3 and FeCl_3 in the presence of an excess BCl_3 in DCM at 45°C (method B). Gratifyingly, this led to exhaustive depolymerization within 22 h yielding mainly MeSiCl_2OH and MeSiCl_3 (1:0.4 molar ratio) (SI, section 12). These functional methylchloro(hydrido)-monosilanes are important Si building blocks used for the preparation of polysiloxanes by the silicone industry for application in, e.g., household consumables, biomedical coatings, or as mouldings, adhesives, composites, sealants and resins by key industry sectors (building, automotive or electronics). Likewise, when a T-type Si resin sample (independently prepared from the hydrolysis of MeSiCl_3) was subjected to method B (SI, section 12),

the same depolymerization mixture was obtained, further confirming the robustness of our new approach in degrading highly cross-linked Si resins [39]. Although a stoichiometric excess of BCl_3 was employed to ensure complete depolymerization on a laboratory scale, the high volatility of the reagents and the selective formation of monomeric chlorosilanes (e.g., MeSiCl_3) make this process highly amenable to standard industrial recycling and fractional distillation (see SI-section 12, for a detailed discussion on scalability and atom economy).

3 | Conclusion

To conclude, we have developed a novel, transition metal free method for hydrogen generation through silane hydrolysis, which significantly outperforms known metal-free, and even transition metal mediated systems (Table S2). These outstanding kinetics stem from the accelerating effect induced by the combined use of DMSO and KOtBu/KOH. By a combined experimental, mechanistic and computational approach, an ionic mechanism involving a key pentavalent anionic Si intermediate is proposed. However, given the apparent complexity of such a system, in-depth computations are underway to delineate the possible synergistic effect of DMSO, silane and KOtBu/KOH [48].

We have described an innovative approach integrating hydrogen generation with silicon-waste valorization using two affordable feedstocks: seawater and PMHS as polysiloxane industry waste. The method is highly efficient, cost-effective, eco-friendly and potentially scalable, since only a simple base catalyst (e.g., KOH) and DMSO as co-solvent are required for generating as much as 1600 mL hydrogen within one minute, using untreated seawater. Recycling of the silicone resin that was co-generated in the process was readily achieved by depolymerization to afford MeSiCl_2OH and MeSiCl_3 , two monomers of high-value for the

silicone industry. These achievements showcase the potential for our process to be applied in rapid on-demand hydrogen generation for energy or chemical feedstock purposes integrated with silicone waste valorization at silicone production factories that are located nearby seashore sites. Moreover, ongoing work addresses involvement of other proton sources derived from waste biomass, with the vision to boost the circular and bioeconomy.

In addition to these advantages, the silane/seawater system drastically limits safety hazards and environmental impact associated with hydrogen generation (e.g., low temperatures, no CO₂ release). As such, our findings should be of particular interest to those seeking to rapidly generate H₂ on-demand and on-site in an eco-friendly manner. Besides, given the location of a large part of industrial silicone production in close proximity of seawater, our process would provide an attractive alternative to current waste disposal strategies.

Author Contributions

Katalin Barta: supervision, conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, writing - original draft, writing - review and editing. **Daniel Legenstein:** investigation, software, validation, writing - review and editing. **Anja Steinmaurer:** investigation, methodology, validation, writing - review and editing. **Philipp Jernej:** investigation, validation, writing - review and editing. **Mustapha Hamdaoui:** conceptualization, methodology, data curation, investigation, validation, formal analysis, supervision, visualization, writing - review and editing, writing - original draft. **Peter Hartmann:** investigation, methodology, software, validation, writing - review and editing. **Adrian Daniel Boese:** supervision, conceptualization, resources, writing - review and editing.

Acknowledgements

Support from the European Research Council (ERC Consolidator grant agreement ID: 101126170) and from the FWF Cluster of Excellence COE 17, Circular Bioengineering (Funding DOI: 10.55776/COE17) is gratefully acknowledged. The authors thank Prof. Klaus Zangger & his group from the University of Graz (Austria) for NMR support. Prof. Dr. Georg Gescheidt and Dr. Dmytro Neshchadin from TU Graz (Austria) are thanked for their valuable support in EPR spectroscopy. Prof. Dr. Walter Gössler from the University of Graz (Austria) is thanked for his support with the ICP analysis. We thank A. Marko and H.M.R. Wilkening (TU Graz) for the ²⁹Si NMR measurements. Federico Rossi is thanked for conducting one control experiment for this study. The authors thank Dr. Jacquin October, Prof. Dr. Aaron Socha and Dr. Claire Cobley for their valuable feedback about the manuscript.

Open access funding provided by Universitat Graz.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Data Availability Statement

The data that supports the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article

References

1. S. Harichandan and S. K. Kar, "Financing the Hydrogen Industry: Exploring Demand and Supply Chain Dynamics," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 32 (2023): 13281–13298.

2. N. Johnson, M. Liebreich, D. M. Kammen, P. Ekins, R. McKenna, and I. Staffell, "Realistic Roles for Hydrogen in the Future Energy Transition," *Nature Reviews Clean Technology* 1 (2025): 351–371, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44359-025-00050-4>.
3. International Energy Agency (IEA), "Global hydrogen demand in the Net Zero Scenario, 2022–2050", can be found under <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/global-hydrogen-demand-in-the-net-zero-scenario-2022-2050>, IEA Paris, 2023 (accessed: July 21, 2025).
4. International Energy Agency (IEA), "Global Hydrogen Review 2024", can be found under <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/89c1e382-dc59-46ca-aa47-9f7d41531ab5/GlobalHydrogenReview2024.pdf>, 2024 (accessed: June 27, 2025).
5. International Energy Agency (IEA), "The Future of Hydrogen", can be accessed under <https://www.iea.org/reports/the-future-of-hydrogen>, 2019 (accessed: July, 2025).
6. M. Nielsen, E. Alberico, W. Baumann, et al., "Low-temperature Aqueous-phase Methanol Dehydrogenation to Hydrogen and Carbon Dioxide," *Nature* 495 (2013): 85–89, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11891>.
7. M. Andérez-Fernández, L. K. Vogt, S. Fischer, et al., "A Stable Manganese Pincer Catalyst for the Selective Dehydrogenation of Methanol," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 56 (2017): 559–562, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201610182>.
8. D. Wei, R. Sang, P. Sponholz, H. Junge, and M. Beller, "Reversible Hydrogenation of Carbon Dioxide to Formic Acid Using a Mn-pincer Complex in the Presence of Lysine," *Nature Energy* 7 (2022): 438–447, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-022-01019-4>.
9. K. Kuciński, H. Stachowiak-Dłużyńska, and G. Hreczycho, "Catalytic Silylation of O-nucleophiles via Si–H or Si–C Bond Cleavage: A Route to Silyl Ethers, Silanols and Siloxanes," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* 459 (2022): 214456.
10. X. L. Luo and R. H. Crabtree, "Homogeneous Catalysis of Silane Alcoholysis via Nucleophilic Attack by the Alcohol on an Ir(eta-2-HSiR₃) Intermediate Catalyzed by [IrH₂S₂(PPh₃)₂]SbF₆ (S = solvent)," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 111 (1989): 2527–2535, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00189a026>.
11. E. Matarasso-Tchiroukhine, "AreneCr(CO)₂ (η²-HSiHPh₂) Complexes as Catalysts for the Si–H Bond Activation. Hydrolysis of the Si–H Bond and Dehydrogenative Coupling Between Diphenylsilane and Nucleophiles," *Journal of the Chemical Society, Chemical Communications* 0 (1990): 681–682, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C39900000681>.
12. D. V. Gutsulyak, S. F. Vyboishchikov, and G. I. Nikonov, "Cationic Silane σ-Complexes of Ruthenium With Relevance to Catalysis," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 132 (2010): 5950–5951, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja101583m>.
13. K. Garcés, F. J. Fernández-Alvarez, V. Polo, R. Lalrempuia, J. J. Pérez-Torrente, and L. A. Oro, "Iridium-Catalyzed Hydrogen Production From Hydrosilanes and Water," *Chemcatchem* 6 (2014): 1691–1697.
14. W. Sattler and G. Parkin, "Zinc Catalysts for on-Demand Hydrogen Generation and Carbon Dioxide Functionalization," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 134 (2012): 17462–17465, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja308500s>.
15. M. Hamdaoui, M. Ney, V. Sarda, et al., "Evidence of a Donor–Acceptor (Ir–H)→SiR₃ Interaction in a Trapped Ir(III) Silane Catalytic Intermediate," *Organometallics* 35 (2016): 2207–2223, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.organomet.6b00248>.
16. D. Ventura-Espinosa, S. Sabater, A. Carretero-Cerdán, M. Baya, and J. A. Mata, "High Production of Hydrogen on Demand From Silanes Catalyzed by Iridium Complexes as a Versatile Hydrogen Storage System," *ACS Catalysis* 8 (2018): 2558–2566, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.7b04479>.
17. U. Prieto-Pascual, A. Rodríguez-Diéguez, Z. Freixa, and M. A. Huertos, "Tailor-Made Synthesis of Hydrosilanol, Hydrosiloxanes, and Silane-diols Catalyzed by Di-Silyl Rhodium(III) and Iridium(III) Complexes,"

- Inorganic Chemistry* 62 (2023): 3095–3105, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.2c03953>.
18. N. Almenara, M. A. Garralda, X. Lopez, J. M. Matxain, Z. Freixa, and M. A. Huertos, "Hydrogen Tunneling in Catalytic Hydrolysis and Alcoholysis of Silanes," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 134 (2022): e202204558, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.202204558>.
 19. E. Antico, M. Leutzsch, N. Wessel, T. Weyhermüller, C. Werlé, and W. Leitner, "Selective Oxidation of Silanes Into Silanols With Water Using [MnBr(CO)₅] as a Precatalyst," *Chemical Science* 14 (2023): 54–60, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2SC05959B>.
 20. A. Luque-Gómez, D. Barrena-Espés, P. García-Orduña, et al., "A Homobimetallic Frustrated Lewis Pair Cobalt Catalyst for the Methanolysis of Hydrosilanes," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 64 (2025): e202513522, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202513522>.
 21. M. Jeon, J. Han, and J. Park, "Catalytic Synthesis of Silanols From Hydrosilanes and Applications," *ACS Catalysis* 2 (2012): 1539–1549, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cs300296x>.
 22. E. A. Ison, R. A. Corbin, and M. M. Abu-Omar, "Hydrogen Production From Catalytic Oxidation of Organosilanes Using a Cationic Oxo-rhenium Catalyst," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 127 (2005): 11938–11939, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja053860u>.
 23. HSL Technologies (formerly HySiLabs), "Liquid Hydrogen Carrier Technology" can be found under <https://hsl.tech/> (accessed April 2026).
 24. A. A. Toutov, W.-B. Liu, K. N. Betz, A. Fedorov, B. M. Stoltz, and R. H. Grubbs, "Silylation of C–H Bonds in Aromatic Heterocycles by an Earth-abundant Metal Catalyst," *Nature* 518 (2015): 80–84, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14126>.
 25. W.-B. Liu, D. P. Schuman, Y.-F. Yang, et al., "Potassium Tert -Butoxide-Catalyzed Dehydrogenative C–H Silylation of Heteroaromatics: A Combined Experimental and Computational Mechanistic Study," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 139 (2017): 6867–6879, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.6b13031>.
 26. S. Banerjee, Y.-F. Yang, I. D. Jenkins, et al., "Ionic and Neutral Mechanisms for C–H Bond Silylation of Aromatic Heterocycles Catalyzed by Potassium Tert -Butoxide," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 139 (2017): 6880–6887, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.6b13032>.
 27. A. A. Toutov, K. N. Betz, M. C. Haibach, A. M. Romine, and R. H. Grubbs, "Sodium Hydroxide Catalyzed Dehydrocoupling of Alcohols With Hydrosilanes," *Organic Letters* 18 (2016): 5776–5779, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.6b01687>.
 28. H. Wu, L.-L. Zhang, J. Wang, et al., "Room-temperature Quasi-catalytic Hydrogen Generation From Waste and Water," *Green Chemistry* 23 (2021): 7528–7533, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC02722K>.
 29. V. Lê, M.-A. Dourges, J.-L. Bobet, and H. Deleuze, "An Innovative Approach for on-demand Hydrogen Generation, and Its Application to the Preparation of Kraft Black Liquor Foams," *New Journal of Chemistry* 44 (2020): 17518–17522.
 30. J. M. Brunel, "Polysilanes: The Grail for a Highly-neglected Hydrogen Storage Source," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 42 (2017): 23004–23009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.07.206>.
 31. C. P. Yap, H. T. Poh, and W. Y. Fan, "Metal-free Catalytic Hydrogen Production From a Polymethylhydrosilane–water Mixture," *RSC Advances* 6 (2016): 5903–5906, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA23887K>.
 32. D. Limnios and C. G. Kokotos, "Organocatalytic Oxidation of Organosilanes to Silanols," *ACS Catalysis* 3 (2013): 2239–2243, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cs400515w>.
 33. D. Prat, A. Wells, J. Hayler, et al., "CHEM21 selection Guide of Classical- and Less Classical-solvents," *Green Chemistry* 18 (2016): 288–296, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5GC01008J>.
 34. G. Durin, A. Fontaine, J. C. Berthet, E. Nicolas, P. Thuéry, and T. Cantat, "Metal-Free Catalytic Hydrogenolysis of Silyl Triflates and Halides Into Hydrosilanes**," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 61 (2022): e202200911, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202200911>.
 35. R. Vidal, J.-A. Alberola-Borràs, S. N. Habisreutinger, et al., "Assessing Health and Environmental Impacts of Solvents for Producing Perovskite Solar Cells," *Nature Sustainability* 4 (2020): 277–285, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00645-8>.
 36. J. Sherwood, T. J. Farmer, and J. H. Clark, "Catalyst: Possible Consequences of the N-Methyl Pyrrolidone REACH Restriction," *Chemistry* 4 (2018): 2010–2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chempr.2018.08.035>.
 37. F. P. Byrne, S. Jin, G. Paggiola, et al., "Tools and Techniques for Solvent Selection: Green Solvent Selection Guides," *Sustainable Chemical Processes* 4 (2016): 7, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40508-016-0051-z>.
 38. J. M. Lavis and R. E. Maleczka, "Polymethylhydrosiloxane," *Encyclopedia of Reagents for Organic Synthesis* (2003): 1–20, <https://doi.org/10.1002/047084289X.rm00062>.
 39. N. Đ. Vű, A. Boulegue-Mondière, N. Durand, et al., "Gallium-catalyzed recycling of silicone waste With boron trichloride to yield key chlorosilanes," *Science* 388 (2025): 392–400.
 40. W. N. Olmstead, Z. Margolin, and F. G. Bordwell, "Acidities of Water and Simple Alcohols in Dimethyl Sulfoxide Solution," *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* 45 (1980): 3295–3299, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo01304a032>.
 41. F. G. Bordwell and D. Algrim, "Nitrogen Acids. I. Carboxamides and Sulfonamides," *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* 41 (1976): 2507–2508, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo00876a042>.
 42. K. Senapati, "Polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS)," *Synlett* 2005 (2005): 1960–1961, <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2005-871948>.
 43. L. D. Field, B. A. Messerle, M. Rehr, L. P. Soler, and T. W. Hambley, "Cationic Iridium(I) Complexes as Catalysts for the Alcoholysis of Silanes," *Organometallics* 22 (2003): 2387–2395, <https://doi.org/10.1021/om020938w>.
 44. S. Siegel and G. V. Smith, "The Stereochemistry of the Hydrogenation of Cycloolefins on Supported Palladium Catalysts^{1,2}," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 82 (1960): 6087–6090, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja01508a028>.
 45. N. Sakai, R. Shimada, and Y. Ogiwara, "Indium-Catalyzed Deoxygenation of Sulfoxides With Hydrosilanes," *Asian Journal of Organic Chemistry* 10 (2021): 845–850, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajoc.202100063>.
 46. Z. Novák, R. Adamik, J. T. Csenki, et al., "Revisiting the Amine-catalysed Cross-coupling," *Nature Catalysis* 4 (2021): 991–993, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41499-021-00709-8>.
 47. N. E. Leadbeater, "When Is Free Really Free?," *Nature Chemistry* 2 (2010): 1007–1009, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.913>.
 48. I. D. Jenkins, K. H. Chow, and E. H. Krenske, "Mechanism of the Stoltz–Grubbs (KO^t Bu/Et₃ SiH) Silylation: Single-Electron Transfer Is the Missing Link Between the Heterolytic and Radical Pathways," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 64 (2025): e202517336, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202517336>.
 49. G. Nocera, A. Young, F. Palumbo, et al., "Electron Transfer Reactions: KO^t Bu (but not NaO^t Bu) Photoreduces Benzophenone Under Activation by Visible Light," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 140 (2018): 9751–9757, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.8b06089>.
 50. M. E. Budén, J. I. Bardagi, M. Puiatti, and R. A. Rossi, "Initiation in Photoredox C–H Functionalization Reactions. Is Dimsyl Anion a Key Ingredient?," *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* 82 (2017): 8325–8333.
 51. C. Chuit, R. J. P. Corriu, C. Reye, and J. C. Young, "Reactivity of Penta- and Hexacoordinate Silicon Compounds and Their Role as Reaction Intermediates," *Chemical Reviews* 93 (1993): 1371–1448, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr00020a003>.
 52. R. Corriu, C. Guérin, B. Henner, and Q. Wang, "Hydrosilicates: A New Class of Pentacoordinated Silicon Derivatives With Unusual Properties," *Inorganica Chimica Acta* 198–200 (1992): 705–713, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-1693\(00\)92415-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-1693(00)92415-0).

53. W. Xie, S.-W. Park, H. Jung, D. Kim, M.-H. Baik, and S. Chang, "Conjugate Addition of Perfluoroarenes to α,β -Unsaturated Carbonyls Enabled by an Alkoxide-Hydrosilane System: Implication of a Radical Pathway," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 140 (2018): 9659–9668, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.8b05744>.
54. E. P. A. Couzijn, M. Schakel, F. J. J. De Kanter, et al., "Dynamic Configurational Isomerism of a Stable Pentaorganosilicate," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 43 (2004): 3440–3442, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.200353006>.
55. N. Kano, H. Miyake, K. Sasaki, T. Kawashima, N. Mizorogi, and S. Nagase, "Dianionic Species With a Bond Consisting of Two Pentacoordinated Silicon Atoms," *Nature Chemistry* 2 (2010): 112–116, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.513>.
56. D. Martin, A. Weise, and H. J. Niclas, "The Solvent Dimethyl Sulfoxide," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 6 (1967): 318–334, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.196703181>.
57. A. J. Parker, "The Effects of Solvation on the Properties of Anions in Dipolar Aprotic Solvents," *Quarterly Reviews, Chemical Society* 16 (1962): 163, <https://doi.org/10.1039/qr9621600163>.
58. C. F. Bernasconi, M. Kaufmann, and H. Zollinger, "Der Einfluss von Dimethylsulfoxid und Dioxan auf die Reaktionen von 2,4-Dinitrofluorbenzol und 2,4-Dinitrochlorbenzol mit Piperidin in Benzol. 4. Mitteilung über Nucleophile Aromatische Substitutionsreaktionen," *Helvetica Chimica Acta* 49 (1966): 2563–2570, <https://doi.org/10.1002/hlca.19660490820>.
59. E. D. Voronova, I. E. Golub, A. Pavlov, et al., "Dichotomous Si–H Bond Activation by Alkoxide and Alcohol in Base-Catalyzed Dehydrocoupling of Silanes," *Inorganic Chemistry* 59 (2020): 12240–12251, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.0c01293>.
60. R. H. Crabtree, P. E. M. Siegbahn, O. Eisenstein, A. L. Rheingold, and T. F. Koetzle, "A New Intermolecular Interaction: Unconventional Hydrogen Bonds With Element–Hydride Bonds as Proton Acceptor," *Accounts of Chemical Research* 29 (1996): 348–354, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar950150s>.
61. T. B. Richardson, S. de Gala, R. H. Crabtree, and P. E. M. Siegbahn, "Unconventional Hydrogen Bonds: Intermolecular B–H...C...C...H–N Interactions," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 117 (1995): 12875–12876, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00156a032>.
62. H. Xie, Z. Zhao, T. Liu, et al., "A Membrane-based Seawater Electrolyser for Hydrogen Generation," *Nature* 612 (2022): 673–678, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05379-5>.
63. S. Waiba, M. Banerjee, L. Frederiksen, et al., "Seawater to Sustainable Fuel: Sunlight-Driven Green Hydrogen Generation With an Atomically Dispersed Photocatalyst," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 147 (2025): 40282–40295, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5c11004>.
64. F. Schüth and S. A. Schunk, "Transitioning of the Chemical Industry toward a Net-Zero Carbon Dioxide Emission Path," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 65 (2025): e22234.
65. R. R. Beswick, A. M. Oliveira, and Y. Yan, "Does the Green Hydrogen Economy Have a Water Problem?," *ACS Energy Letters* 6 (2021): 3167–3169, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.1c01375>.
66. L. Rösch, P. John, and R. Reitmeier, *Silicones. In Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry* (Wiley-VCH).
67. A. Provatas and J. G. Matison, "Silsequioxanes: Synthesis and Applications," *Trends in polymer science* 5 (1997): 327–332.
68. J. J. Chruściel, "Silicon-Based Polymers and Materials, De Gruyter," (2022): 20–182, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110643671>.
69. S. Venkatraman and R. Gale, "Skin Adhesives and Skin Adhesion," *Biomaterials* 19 (1998): 1119–1136, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612\(98\)00020-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612(98)00020-9).
70. Wacker Chemie AG, "Durability enhancement for cementitious materials through waterproofing by organosilicon chemistry", can be found under https://www.zkg.de/en/artikel/zkg_Durability_enhancement_for_cementitious_materials_through_waterproofing_by-3562203.html, *Construction Silicones*, Wacker Chemie AG, Munich/Germany, 2020 (accessed: August 2, 2025).
71. M. Itoh, F. Oka, M. Suto, S. D. Cook, and N. Auner, "Characterization and some Insights Into the Reaction Chemistry of Polymethylsilsequioxane or Methyl Silicone Resins," *The International Journal of Polymer Science* 2012 (2012): 526795.
72. P. Döhler and S. Enthaler, "Conversion of Poly (methylhydrosiloxane) Waste to Useful Commodities," *Catalysis Letters* 146 (2016): 345–352.
73. B. Rupasinghe and J. C. Furgal, "Full Circle Recycling of Polysiloxanes via Room-Temperature Fluoride-Catalyzed Depolymerization to Repolymerizable Cyclics," *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* 3 (2021): 1828–1839, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsapm.0c01406>.
74. D. J. Krug, M. Z. Asuncion, and R. M. Laine, "Facile Approach to Recycling Highly Cross-Linked Thermoset Silicone Resins Under Ambient Conditions," *ACS Omega* 4 (2019): 3782–3789, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.8b02927>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: anie73011-sup-0001-SuppMat.pdf.

Supporting File 2: anie73011-sup-0002-Movie S1.mp4.